

Enhancing Employee Performance: The Impact of Workplace Counselling Programs at Hasbah Kenya Limited

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Publication Date: 2025/02/07

Abstract: Workplace counselling is the offering of mental health support to the employees or team as funded by the organization. Despite the employee counselling programs in place, issues such as substance abuse/dependence, absenteeism, work related accidents, and increased medical costs, among others, remain common among organizations' employees. Such issues contribute to reduced job performance and adversely affect the psychological health of employees. . The study adopted a correlational research design and was anchored on the social exchange theory, stakeholders theory, and goal-freedom theory. The study targeted 178 employees of Hasbah Kenya limited. The study used the sample of 90 employees sampled using proportionate stratified sampling. Primary data was collected using structured and semi-structured questionnaires. Pilot test was conducted with 10% of the population hence 18 employees. The study used content and construct validity. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha indicated an overall high 0.841 questionnaire reliability score. Data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23. The findings were presented in tables. The unstandardized coefficient for health related problem counselling ($\beta = 0.497$, $p = 0.078$) indicating that for each unit increase in health related problem counselling, employee performance increases by approximately 0.497 units, The study recommends the organization should focus on enhancing the practices on health related counseling. The organization need to create a forum where employees freely give views on the specific challenges and barriers in accessing health related problem counseling programs.

Keyword: Health Related Problems Counselling, Performance.

How to Cite: Ali Nuru Fozia; Dr. Oloo Caroline (2025). Enhancing Employee Performance: The Impact of Workplace Counselling Programs at Hasbah Kenya Limited. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 10(1), 1837-1846. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14810227>

I. INTRODUCTION

Programs for employee counselling help resolve issues with employees that impact their ability to do their jobs. Workplace counselling was initially created to treat drug and alcohol issues among employees (Bryant-Jefferies, 2019). Nangoy et al. (2020) state that as time has passed, their purpose has broadened to include a broader range of requirements. These counselling programs address a variety of needs for these personnel, such as marital and family issues, money troubles, legal issues, stress, anxiety, depression, and other emotional disturbances. Marescaux et al. (2019) claim that contemporary counselling services address concerns that arise in both the home and workplace for workers.

Most businesses in Africa have adopted the idea of offering employee counselling services. Omoegun, et al. (2018) study in Nigeria found that many business firms in the country need to be made aware of the benefits and

significance of workplace counselling. They also need to understand the advantages of hiring workplace counsellors for their businesses, especially for workers who struggle with emotional issues. When workplace counselling is effectively provided or presented to employees, Kaoma (2022) discovered that workers in Zambia reported numerous benefits, such as bettering their lives and fostering a positive work environment.

➤ Employee Performance

Effective performance is usually a combination of many factors, working together so that an employee can be the most successful he or she can be. According to Atatsi et al. (2019), when the term performance is used in an organizational context it refers to employee performance which is likened to the collective talents, efforts, and abilities of all employees put together with day-to-day efficacy that have added more productive output and goal achievement within an organization. Employee performance is one of the key attributes that affects the effectiveness and

performance of an organization. Training and development, acts as a major performance-changing catalyst for learning organizations (Parashakti et al., 2020). Essentially, management standards should be such that they provide a true reflection about the performance and also help in comparing it with the benchmarks and raising the standard of performance process. These will determine the outputs and the evaluation of this performance such that any discrepancies are noticed. It will then help to bring back those outputs to at least near levels that are desired by the organization (Muchiri, 2022).

The internal satisfaction of the employees with their jobs directly affects performance levels. This indicates that the happier employees are with their job or company, the more they will do well to achieve organizational goals (Mira et al. 2019). Employers have established that healthy

employees are a source of a competitive advantage and improved performance. For example, well-designed workplace counselling programs could help organizations boost the morale of employees, reduce stress, improve teamwork, and enhance productivity. Equally, Employee counselling programs could guide employees make healthy and smart choices that can lessen healthcare costs, diminish absenteeism, and increase vitality. Despite the Employee counselling programs in place, issues such as substance abuse/dependence, substance abuse among employees persists, suggesting that current counselling efforts may not be effectively addressing or preventing dependency issues absenteeism, high rates of absenteeism remain an issue, impacting productivity and potentially indicating that employees may not be engaging fully with or benefiting from available support services.

Fig 1. Conceptual Framework on Health-Related Problem Counselling

The conceptual model explained the association of work place programs and employee performance. The health-related problem counselling program aims to create a safe workplace by implementing a drug-free policy, providing education on substance abuse, and offering support resources (Nga et al., 2013). Additionally, the program promotes awareness of occupational illnesses and wellness through health screenings and mental health support initiatives. It includes workshops on understanding

personality types, enhancing interpersonal skills, and building resilience against stress and burnout. Additionally, the program offers access to counselling services and stress management techniques to help employees navigate personal challenges effectively. The study aimed to address three main questions: whether pre-purchase counselling reduces 90-day delinquency rates, how different counselling types compare in effectiveness, and if certain providers are more effective than others. The findings showed that

counselling significantly reduces mortgage delinquency, with borrowers who received counselling experiencing an average 19% decrease in 90-day delinquency rates. Individual counselling programs were particularly effective, yielding a 34% reduction, while classroom and home study programs resulted in reductions of 26% and 21%, respectively.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study adopted a correlational research design. The research identified and focused on key variables related to workplace counselling programs and employee performance. The study utilized structured questionnaires to gather numerical data. Participants, including employees and managers at Hasbah Kenya Limited, responded to future-focused questions, allowing for the establishment of correlations between counselling program variables and employee performance indicators. The research employed correlation coefficient analysis to quantify the strength and direction of relationships between variables (Luo et al., 2018). Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to measure the linear correlation between the independent and dependent variables, for example, the number of counselling sessions attended and improvements in employee performance metrics. The research design segmented participants based on relevant characteristics such as job roles, departments, or counselling program utilization patterns.

The target population consists of employees from Hasbah company, with a specific focus on 178 employees, from which 90 was selected from various departments. Stratified random sampling was used since this method involves dividing the employee population at Hasbah Kenya Limited into different strata or subgroups based on departments and roles.

The researcher adopted Yamane's formulae
 $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$

Where n is the sample size, N is the population size and e is the margin of error.

➤ Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by the Maseno University School of Graduate studies and cleared by the University Ethical Review Committee.

➤ Reliability & Validity Instruments

Cronbach's Alpha was calculated. An acceptably higher Cronbach's Alpha value, typically above 0.7, suggests that the items on the instrument measure the same underlying construct (Mehari et al., 2021). During the literature review the researcher developed a complete register of the health related, work related and personal issue problem counselling and employee performance. This literature formed the basis for the drafting of the questionnaires. The developed questionnaire was presented to two experts for critique. This procedure of expert assessment was repeated until there was total agreement between the two experts. The document was piloted two weeks prior to actual data collection.

➤ Statistical Analysis

Data analysis and presentation are critical components in understanding the influence of workplace counseling programs on employee performance Hasbah Kenya Limited. The research design incorporates quantitative data collection methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Multiple regression analysis was utilized to test cross sectional data:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon$$

III. RESULTS

➤ Respondents Demographic Characteristics

The demographic features of the respondents encompassed their gender, age, their occupation, the number of years they have been employed, and their highest degree of educational attainment. The results are displayed in Table 1, utilizing frequency counts and percentages.

Table 1. Respondents Demographic Characteristics

No	Demographic	Frequency	Percent
1	Gender		
	Male	42	60
	Female	28	40
2	Age (yrs)		
	18-30	7	10
	31-40	20	28.6
	41-50	28	40.0
	51 and above	15	21.4
3	Department		
	Transport	39	55.7
	Sales	27	38.6
	Accounts	4	5.7
4	Occupation		
	Driver	34	48.6

	Sales Rep	24	34.3
	Mechanics	5	7.1
	Management	3	4.3
	Accountant	4	5.7
5	Number of years worked (yrs)		
	Less than 1	1	1.4
	1-2	11	15.7
	3-4	23	32.9
	5yr and above	35	50
6	Highest Education Level		
	Certificate	33	47.1
	Diploma	23	32.9
	Degree	14	20

It was observed that 42(60%) were male, while 28(40.0%) were female. The largest number of respondents, 28(40%) were aged between 41-50 yrs, 20(28.6%) was aged between 31-40 yrs and 15(21.4%) were aged 51yrs and above. From the finding, it emerged that the majority of the respondents 39 (55.7%) were from the department of transport followed by 27(38.6 %) from the department of sales, 4(5.7%) were in the department of Accounts. As regards the occupation, the majority of the respondents, 34(58.0%) were drivers, followed by 24(34.3%) who were sales representatives, followed by mechanics 5(7.1%), then Accounts 4(5.7%) and the least, 3(4.3%) were management. The findings further shows that majority 35(50 %) of the respondents had 5 years and above of work experience, 23(32.9%) had between 3-4 years, 11(15.7%) had between 1-2years and those with one year experience were only (1.4%). Majority, 33(47.1%) were certificate holders, 23(32.9%) were diploma holders, and 14 (20%) were degree holders. It can be noted that a larger percentage of respondents' qualification of certificate and above hence educated.

➤ *Health Related Problem Counselling and Employee Performance*

The measurement of Health related problem counseling was measured by assessing respondents' ratings on a five-point Likert scale. Participants were requested to express their level of agreement with the statements about health related problem counseling. Each statement was assigned a numerical value ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The results are provided in Table 2 as depicted below.

Table 2: Rating on the Effect of Health related Problem Counselling

Health and Safety	1	2	3	4	5	M	STD
There are health and safety concerns I consider most relevant to my job	0(0)	2(2.9)	3(4.3)	24(34.3)	41(58.6)	4.49	.72
I feel informed about health and safety counseling services available to employees	0(0)	3(4.3)	2(2.9)	12(17.1)	53(75.7)	4.64	.74
There are specific changes in your health and safety practices resulting from counseling participation.	0(0)	0(0)	8(11.4)	16(22.9)	46(65.7)	4.54	.70
There are specific challenges or barriers in accessing health and safety counseling at Hasbah Kenya Limited	4(5.7)	9(12.9)	3(4.3)	10(14.3)	44(62.9)	4.16	1.30
I actively engage with health counseling resources, such as workshops, training sessions, or informational materials	0(0)	0(0)	7(10.0)	12(17.1)	51(72.9)	4.63	.66
The current health counseling programs are in addressing the identified concerns relevant to your job	1(1.4)	1(1.4)	8(11.4)	6(8.6)	54(77.1)	4.73	.74
I have noticed an improvement in my overall well-being as a result of participating in health and safety counseling sessions	1(1.4)	1(1.4)	3(4.3)	6(8.6)	59(84.3)	4.59	.86
Overall						4.54	.817

From the findings, the majority of employees, 41(58.6%) strongly agreed that there are health concerns they consider most relevant to their job, and 24(34.3) agreed to that statement, (M=4.49, STD=0.72). Fifty-three, that is 75.7.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that they feel informed about health counseling services available to them. These were also supported by 12(17.1%) of the participants who agreed thus affirming that they feel informed about health and safety counseling services available to them (M=4.64, STD=.74). Specific changes in their health practices resulting from counseling participation. The findings revealed that the majority, 46(65.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed and 16 (22.9%) agreed that there are specific changes in their health practices resulting from counseling participation (M=4.54, STD=.70). Forty-four, that is 62.9% of the respondents strongly agreed that there are specific challenges or barriers in accessing health counseling. These were also supported by 10(14.3%) who agreed thus affirming the statement that there are specific challenges or barriers in accessing health and safety counseling (M=4.16, STD=1.30)

Further analysis was carried out to establish the individual influence of health related problem counselling on employee performance at Hasbah Ltd. The findings are presented as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Model Coefficient on Health and Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.650	1.268		2.090	.040
	Health	.497	.277	.550	1.792	.078
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance						

The regression analysis results indicate a relationship between health and employee performance. The unstandardized coefficient for health is 0.497, suggesting that for each unit increase in health measures; employee performance is expected to increase by approximately 0.497 units, all else being equal.

➤ *Work-Related Problem Counseling and Employee Performance*

Participants were requested to express their level of agreement with the statements that comprised the work-related problem counselling subscale. Each statement was assigned a numerical range, with 1 representing "Strongly Disagree," 2 representing "Disagree," 3 representing "Neutral," 4 representing "Agree," and 5 representing "Strongly Agree." The results are displayed in Table 4.4 provided below.

Table 4: Rating on Work-Related Problem Counseling

Work-related problem	1	2	3	4	5	M	STD
I encounter work-related problems that impact my job performance	0(0)	2(2.9)	2(2.9)	47(67.1)	19(27.1)	4.19	0.62
The current work-related problem counseling programs are effective.	0(0)	0(0)	3(4.3)	34(48.6)	33(47.1)	4.42	0.58
I feel comfortable discussing work-related problems with the counselors provided.	0(0)	0(0)	1(1.4)	26(37.1)	43(61.5)	4.60	0.52
Addressing work-related problems through counseling positively influences your overall job satisfaction	0(0)	0(0)	2(2.9)	13(18.6)	55(78.5)	4.75	0.49
I have noticed improvements in my job performance after participating in work-related problem counseling sessions.	0(0)	0(0)	2(2.9)	10(14.3)	58(82.8)	4.8	0.47
I am aware of the various channels and resources available for accessing work-related problem counseling.	0(0)	2(2.9)	3(4.3)	10(14.3)	55(78.6)	4.68	0.69
There are additional support or resources that will enhance the effectiveness of work-related problem counseling programs	1(1.4)	1(1.4)	4(5.7)	7(10.0)	57(81.4)	4.68	0.77
Overall						4.58	0.591

From the findings, majority of employees, 47(67.1%) agreed that they encounter work-related problems that impact their job performance (Mean=4.19, Std.Dev=0.65). Thirty-four, that is 35.4% of the respondents agreed that the current work-related problem counseling programs are effective. These were also supported by 33(47.1%) of the participants who strongly agreed thus affirming that the current work-related program counselling is effective (Mean=4.42, Std.Dev =.58). Further analysis was carried out to establish the individual influence of work-related problem counseling on employee performance at Hasbah Ltd. The findings are presented as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Model Coefficient on Influence of Work Related Problem

Model		Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.848	1.940		.437	.663
	Work related problem	.884	.421	.564	2.098	.040
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance						

The results from the regression analysis reveal insights into the relationship between work-related problems and employee performance. The unstandardized coefficient for work-related problems is 0.884, indicating that for each unit increase in work-related problems, employee performance increases by approximately 0.884 units, assuming all other factors are held constant.

➤ *Personal Issue Counselling and Employee Performance*

To the establish the influence of personal issues counseling on the performance of employees at Hasbah Kenya Limited. The first step was to establish respondents rating on years of work experience and related aspects of experience. Therefore, respondents were asked “To what extent do you agree with the following statements?” Each statement was assigned a range of values, with 1 representing "Strongly Disagree," 2 representing "Disagree," 3 representing "Neither," 4 representing "Agree," and 5 representing "Strongly Agree." The results are displayed in Table 6, utilizing frequency counts, percentages, averages, and standard deviations.

Table 6: Rating on Personal Issues Counseling

Years of Work Experience	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	Std.Dev
I often utilize personal issues counseling services provided by the company.	1(1.4)	1(4)	6(8.6)	16(22.9)	46(65.7)	4.50	.83
I believe personal issues counseling has helped me manage stress at work.	0(0)	0(0)	3(4.3)	19(27.1)	48(68.6)	4.64	.57
Personal issues counseling has impacted my productivity at work	1(1.4)	1(1.4)	3(4.3)	8(11.4)	57(81.4)	4.70	.75
I feel more focused and motivated at work after receiving personal issues counseling	2(2.9)	0(0)	2(2.9)	7 (10.0)	59(84.3)	4.73	.78
Employees always prioritize professional attitude at work.	2(2.9)	0(0)	2(2.9)	6(8.6)	60(85.7)	4.73	.77
Overall						4.66	.74

It was observed that majority of employees, 46(65.7%) strongly agreed that they often utilize personal issues counseling services provided by the company, and 16(22.9) agreed to that statement, (Mean=4.50, Std.Dev=0.83). Forty-eight, that is 68.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that they believe personal issues counseling has helped them manage stress at work. These were also supported by 19(27.1%) of the participants who agreed thus affirming that they believe personal issues counseling has helped them manage stress at work. (Mean=4.64, Std. Dev =.57). Further analysis was carried out to establish the individual influence of health and safety on employee performance at Hasbah Ltd. The findings are presented as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Model Coefficient on Personal Issue on Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.253	1.093		1.147	.256
	Personal,issues counseling	.783	.232	.624	3.374	.001
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance						

The regression analysis results indicate a relationship between personal issues and employee performance. The unstandardized coefficient for personal issues is 0.783, suggesting that for each unit increase in personal issues measures; employee performance is expected to increase by approximately 0.783 units, all else being equal. This positive association implies that improvements in personal counselling may contribute to enhanced employee performance.

➤ *Employee Performance*

Five sub-scales or indicators of employee performance were teamwork, productivity, professionalism, number of accidents, and medical costs. Respondents were therefore asked to rate the extent to which they agreed with statements on employees' performance. Each statement was assigned a range of values, with 1 representing Strongly Disagree, 2 representing; Disagree, 3 representing Neutral 4 representing Agree, and 5 representing Strongly Agree. The results are displayed in Table 8 utilizing frequency counts, percentages, averages, and standard deviations.

Table 8: Rating on Employee Performance

Employee Performance	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	Std.dev
Goal achievement level has improved	1(1.4)	0(0)	0(0)	7(10)	62(88.6)	4.84	.55
There is improved teamwork	1(1.4)	1(1.4)	1(1.4)	16(22.9)	51(72.9)	4.64	.72
Employees productivity has improved	1(1.4)	0(0)	1(1.4)	12(17.1)	56(80.1)	4.74	.62
Professionalism has improved	1(1.4)	0(0)	1(1.4)	6 (8.6)	62(88.6)	4.83	.58
Number of accidents have reduced	1(1.4)	0(0)	1(1.4)	11(15.7)	57(81.4)	4.76	.62

Medical cost has reduced	1(1.4)	0(0)	1(1.4)	12(17.1)	56(80.1)	4.74	.62
Overall						4.76	0.618

From the findings, the majority of employees, 62 (88.6%) strongly agreed that goal achievement level has improved, and 7(10%) agreed to that statement, (mean=4.84, std.dev=0.55). fifty-one, that is 72.9 % of the respondents strongly agreed that there is improved teamwork. These were also supported by 16(22.9%) of the participants who agreed thus affirming that there is improved teamwork (mean=4.64, std.dev=.72).

➤ *Regression Analysis*

A standard multiple regression analysis was conducted using employee performance as the dependent variable, and the three independence variables: Work related problem issue counseling, Health related problem counselling, and personal issue counselling as the predicting variables. The research used statistical package for social sciences (SPSS V 22) to code, enter and compute the measurements of the multiple regressions. The results are given in the overall model summary in Table 9.

Table 9 Overall Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.586 ^a	.343	.339	.58868	.343	3.847	3	66	.012

a. Predictors: (Constant), work-related problem counseling, Health –related problem counselling, personal issue counselling

The findings show that there is a significant multiple correlation between workplace programs and Employee programs (R=.586). The R square value (0.343) is the result of the squared R-value, which is the coefficient of determination implying that workplace programs account for a 34.3% variance in employee performance. The findings also show a small standard error of the estimate thus implying that the results were more accurate with small errors that are permissible. This means workplace programs account for a significant amount of variance in employee performance.

➤ *Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)*

The study also used the analysis of variance (ANOVA) to check how well the model fits the data and the results are shown below. It’s also used as measure of the goodness of fit i.e. how well the sample chosen explains the true population. If the probability (sig.) is greater than 0.05, it implies that the parameters do not explain the true population. A probability of less than 0.05 implies that the parameter estimates explain the true population. The results are illustrated in Table 10.

Table 10 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.999	3	1.333	3.847	.013 ^b
	Residual	22.872	66	.347		
	Total	26.871	69			

a. Dependent Variable: employee performance
b. Predictors: (Constant), work-related problem counseling, health related problem counselling, personal issue counselling

The study further undertook ANOVA analysis to establish the validity and effectiveness of the model in explaining the relationship between the study variables. Degrees of freedom (df) indicate the number of independent variables. At the same time, the value 66 was obtained by taking the sample response less than the number of independent variables and less than one. The model in Table 4. 12 was found to be valid ($F_{(3,70)} = 3.847, P < .013$) meaning that the independent variables are a good predictor of variations in performance and the model was effective in describing the relationship that exists. The significance value was less than 0.05 indicating that the model was significant.

Table 11. Regression Coefficients Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.673	.537		3.495	0.017
	Work-related problem	.335	0.094	0.416	3.242	0.023
	Health related problem	.278	0.081	0.139	3.215	0.004

	Personal issue counseling	.597	0.078	0.281	4.345	0.001
a. Dependent Variable: employee performance						

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.600	.516		5.037	.000
	Work-related	.011	.084	.013	.134	.004
	health -related	.067	.074	.086	.910	.006
	Personal issues	.421	.064	.630	6.634	.000
a. Dependent Variable: employee performance						

The researcher conducted a multiple regression analysis to determine the relationship between employee performance in Hasbah Kenya Limited and the three variables. As per the SPSS generated table above, the equation ($Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \epsilon$) becomes: $Y = 2.600 + 0.11X_1 + 0.067X_2 + 0.421X_3$. Where Y is the dependent variable (Employee Performance), X_1 is work-related problem counseling, X_2 is health related problem counselling, and X_3 is personal issue counseling. The possible value of Y when all independent variables are equal to zero is 2.600.

IV. DISCUSSION

Participants actively engage with health and safety counseling resources, such as workshops, training sessions, or informational materials. The overall mean of 4.54 therefore indicated that most of the respondents were in agreement that health related problem counselling affect employee performance. Regarding work-related problems counselling, this positive association implies that improvements in health may contribute to enhanced employee performance, potentially reflecting that a safer work environment encourages employees to perform better. Although the p-value for health is 0.078, which exceeds the conventional significance level of 0.05, it still indicates a trend toward significance. The t-value of 1.792 suggests that while the relationship is not statistically significant at the conventional threshold, it is close and may warrant further investigation. This finding highlights the importance of health and safety in the workplace, suggesting that organizations should consider investing in safety measures to potentially boost employee performance (Flemming, 2023). The constant term has a significant p-value of 0.040, indicating that when health measures are absent, the baseline level of employee performance is significantly different from zero, with a value of 2.650. This suggests that even without specific health initiatives, employees may still exhibit some level of performance. However, the findings underscore the need for a more comprehensive approach to exploring the nuances of how health affects performance. Future research could benefit from a larger sample size and the inclusion of additional variables, such as organizational culture and employee engagement, to further elucidate the relationship between health and safety and employee performance (Smith, 2020).

On the statement that the employees feel comfortable discussing work-related problems with the counselors provided. These were also supported by 13(18.6%) who agreed thus affirming the statement that addressing work-related problems through counseling positively influences their overall job satisfaction (Mean=4.75, Std.Dev=0.49). Employees have noticed improvements in their job performance after participating in work-related problem counseling sessions revealed that the majority, 58(82.9%) and 10(14.3%) of the respondents agreed that they have noticed improvements in their job performance after participating in work-related problem counseling sessions, (Mean=4.8, Std.Dev =.47. The overall mean of 4.58 therefore indicated that most of the respondents were in agreement that work place problem counseling influence employee performance. The unstandardized coefficient for work-related problems is 0.884 suggests a positive correlation between the presence of work-related problems and employee performance. The significance value (p-value) indicated that the relationship is statistically significant, suggesting that work-related problems do have a measurable effect on employee performance. The t-value of 2.098 further supports this finding. These results imply that addressing work-related issues could enhance performance, as employees might engage more deeply with their tasks when navigating difficulties. This finding corroborates with the findings of a study conducted by (Amrani et al., 2020.) who posits that counseling can significantly reduce workplace stress, improve employee morale, and enhance productivity by addressing personal and job-related issues in a confidential setting

Fifty-nine, that is 84.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that they feel more focused and motivated at work after receiving personal issues counseling. The significance value for personal issues counseling is 0.001, which is well below the conventional threshold of 0.05, indicating a highly statistically significant relationship. The t-value of 3.374 further supports this finding, suggesting that the effect of personal issues counseling on employee performance is robust and unlikely to have occurred by chance. These results highlight the critical role that personal support services play in fostering a productive work environment, suggesting that organizations could benefit significantly from investing in such counseling programs to optimize employee performance (Jones,2024). In contrast, the

constant term has a non-significant p-value of 0.256, indicating that when personal issues counseling is absent, the baseline level of employee performance does not differ significantly from zero. While this finding suggests that personal issues counselling is a key factor in enhancing employee performance, it also points to the need for a multifaceted approach to employee support that includes additional resources and interventions

Table 11, above shows the regression equation established, taking all factors into account (work-related problem counseling, health related counselling, and personal issue counseling) constant at zero, employee performance will be 2.600. The data findings analyzed also showed that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit increase in work-related counseling will lead to a 0.11 increase in employee performance; a unit increase in health related counselling will lead to a 0.067 increase in employee performance, a unit increase in personal issue counseling will lead to a 0.421 employee performance. This infers that all three variables (work-related, health & safety, and personal issue counseling) contribute to employee performance. At a 5% level of significance and 95% level of confidence, work-related counseling had a p-value of 0.004; health & safety showed a p-value of 0.006, and personal issue counseling showed a p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the most significant factor was personal issue counseling which showed a p-value of 0.000.

V. CONCLUSION

Work related problem counselling is important to the performance of employees as it stands out to be one of the influencers of employee performance. From the current findings, it can be concluded that work related problem counselling has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Work related problem counselling also accounts for a significant amount of variance in employee performance. The study thus concludes that work related problem counselling has a positive and significant influence on employee performance at Hasbah. Health and safety counselling is important to the performance of employees as it stands out to be one of the influencers of employee performance. Health related problem counselling also accounts for a significant amount of variance in employee performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis that Health related problem counselling does not have a significant influence on employee performance is rejected. The study thus concludes that health related problem counselling has a positive and significant influence on employee performance at Hasbah. Personal issues counselling is important to the performance of employees as it stands out to be one of the influencers of employee performance. Personal issues counselling also accounts for a significant amount of variance in employee performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis that personal issues counselling does not have a significant influence on employee performance is rejected. The study thus concludes that health and safety counselling have a positive and significant influence on employee performance at Hasbah.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors are thankful for the volunteers who participated in the study.

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